

WAYS OF IMPLEMENTING MORAL AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN SCHOOL

Shabbazova Dilfuza Ruzikulovna

Head of the Department of Primary Education Theory of
Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Xayitova Xurshida Toshboboyevna

Teacher of the department of pedagogy and psychology of the
Denov Pedagogical College

Abstract: This article contains information on moral upbringing of children at school, teaching process, various district activities outside the classroom and school, raising the level of awareness of students.

Key words: moral education, lesson process, consciousness, conversation, discussion, lecture, moral concept, moral habit.

Moral education of children is carried out in the school, in the course of the lesson, in the classroom and in various district activities outside the school.

Students are given knowledge, (imagination, emotional, image knowledge, information, oral information, understanding, generalized knowledge) skills and habits.

Children are taught about manners and decency. They get moral concepts from fiction and science literature, life, movies and plays. It is necessary to teach students to evaluate their own behavior from the first quality, to make them understand the meaning of love of work, care of property, respect, honesty, integrity, conscience, and modesty. For this, with the students of the upper grades, "Courage and cowardice", "Courage and nobility", "What is collective?", "How do you understand happiness?", "What is the beauty of a person?", "Spiritually mature person", "Human dignity It is good to have a conversation on the topics of value, ethics and personal freedom.

In order to increase the level of consciousness of students, it is necessary to allow them to self-evaluate, to explain that success in study, work, and life depends on oneself.

At the end of the week, "Am I satisfied with last week?", "Should I punish or reward myself?" It is recommended to write an answer to the question. It is analyzed in an educational lesson or in an individual interview.

Educating students in the spirit of morality creates in them the following qualities of free-thinking: striving for a goal, perseverance in studying and work, determination, initiative, organization, fearlessness of difficulties.

Different methods are used in moral education at school. Including:

First of all, the learning process at school should be organized at a high level, as the great German pedagogue A.V. Disterweg showed, a teacher can educate a student well only with good teaching. Sometimes the means of moral influence are not shown enough, they lower the price for the right. They are rude.

Secondly, the success of students and teachers in the process of moral education depends on the level of the team. If the team is moral and harmonious, the children will be disciplined.

Thirdly, the planned and coordinated implementation of educational activities ensures the success of moral education. A.S. Makkarenko says that five teachers with low qualifications are better than 10 highly qualified teachers who work on their own.

Fourth, creating a positive, emotional environment at school has a beneficial effect on the process of moral education.

Fifth, to achieve compliance of all students with the general order and life regime at school.

In moral education, methods such as conversation, debate, lecture are used to form consciousness and moral concepts, and methods of training and conducting children's various activities are used to form moral habits.

It is also important to consider its result in moral education. It is not the number of events that determines the quality. The grade is not complete.

The measure of upbringing is called social activity, positive attitude to demands, ability to evaluate one's right, moral habits and virtues. These cannot be measured.

In fact, social activity, behavior and relationships, spiritual orientation, presence of stable moral qualities can be a measure. Social and political attestation in school life is a form of determining and evaluating moral education. A complete study of the personality determines the education.

The main goal of physical education is to ensure the natural healthy growth of all members of the body of students, to prepare them for mental and physical work, as well as for the defense of the homeland.

Our forefathers, when meeting or saying goodbye, first of all wished good health from the bottom of their hearts. They put the value of being healthy and the value of the family in an honorable place. Our republic is proud of Bahadirs, wrestlers and heroes. Even today, the process of reviving physical culture and sports on a national basis is taking place in all cities and villages of our republic.

Abu Ali ibn Sina, who was named the Aristotle of the East, also listed the following human qualities, such as courage - the courage of a person in doing something, endurance, the power to stop the evil that befalls a person. Discretion is the power to avoid haste in doing something.

Perception is the ability to quickly understand the true meaning of things given by intuition. Alisher Navoi, the Sultan of poetry, in his epic "Farhad and Shirin" pays special attention to Farhad's physical fitness and proudly praises his physical abilities.

It is written in the epic that Farhad began to train not only with mental training, but also with physical and military exercises. Swimming, horse riding, fencing, etc. are his daily activities. At the age of 10, a 20-year-old man has the strength, he amazes people with his mental and physical strength and skills.

According to Abdulla Awlani, it is necessary to educate the body in order to have a healthy mind, good morals, and knowledge. "A healthy and strong body is the most necessary thing for a person. Because in order to read, teach, learn and teach, a person needs strength and a healthy body. People who do not have a healthy body tend to make mistakes in their actions and work. The body and the

soul are like the skin of the right side of a garment. If the body is not decorated with cleanliness, if it is not kept from bad habits, then it is like a busy man who puts on a coat and washes the lining, and the dirt on it is always thrown into it. Work and a healthy body are necessary for education of thought.

Thanks to sports, feeling one's strength and skills with joy, communicating with nature has pleased people since time immemorial. So, as can be seen from the above examples, the mental, moral and physical perfection of a person has been glorified and appreciated in all aspects of the development of human history.

Physical education has a beneficial effect on people, strengthens their health, increases their ability to work, and helps them live longer. Sport is an excellent means of training height and maintaining strength at any age. It helps to alternate between work and rest, serves as a source of creative feelings.

In short, physical culture and sports are one of the social factors that create young people who are healthy, strong, agile, resourceful, able to overcome obstacles, patriots who respect the motherland like the apple of their eye, and who look to the future with confidence.

For this reason, from the most primitive state of human society to the present day, any physical perfection and fullness have been considered as a chain that ensures the perfection of generations.

Therefore, ensuring the physical fitness of the growing young generation is not only the responsibility of parents and schools, but it is also a matter of state importance.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Zarnigor, B., & Ruzikulovna, S. D. (2019). Views Of The Great Thinkers Of The East About Education And Perfection Of Human. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(12).

2. Бабамуратова, З., & Шаббазова, Д. Р. (2019). ВЗГЛЯДЫ ВЕЛИКИХ МЫСЛИТЕЛЕЙ ВОСТОКА О ВОСПИТАНИИ И СОВЕРШЕНСТВЕ

Всяких Максим Владимирович, кандидат экономических наук, 19.

3. Shabbazova, D. (2023). BOSHLANG‘ICH SINIF O‘QUVCHILARI SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISHDA SHAHSIY QADRYATLI YONDASHUV. MONOGRAFIYA. Termiz-2023. Interpretation and Researches, 1(1).

4. Ruzikulovna, S. D. (2021). PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHER AND STUDENT TEACHING ACTIVITIES AND SYSTEM OF PERSONAL VALUES. European Scholar Journal, 2 (7), 32-33.

5. Norqobilova, R. D. (2023). USE of diagnostic tests in foreign schools. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 2(1), 359-364.

6. Norqobilova Rayxona Davlatovna. Functions and Principles of Pedagogical Diagnostics. Vol. 2 No. 1 (2023): Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal.

7. Норқобилова, Р. (2023). Boshlang ‘ich sinf o ‘quvchilarining ona tilidan iqtidorini diagnostika qilish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish. *Общество и инновации*, 4(1/S), 36-41.

8. Abdullayeva, S. A., & Norqobilova, R. D. (2023). BOSHLANG ‘ICH SINIF O ‘QUVCHILARINING BILIM O‘ZLASHTIRISHLARINI DIAGNOSTIKA QILISH. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).